

Formulation of a Novel Herbal Based Liniment for Muscle Aches and Pain

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to formulate a novel herbal-based liniment for muscle aches using a combination of *Lepidium Sativum* seed extract, sandalwood, Aswagandha, rubbing alcohol, marshmallow root, and Poblano pepper. The liniment is intended to provide relief from muscle soreness, inflammation, and discomfort. In this research, we will investigate the individual and synergistic effects of these herbal ingredients on muscle pain relief and assess the liniment's potential for promoting muscle recovery and relaxation. The will be optimized through experimental design, and its potency and safety will be investigated by various *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies. As I study the results will contribute to the development of a natural and effective liniment for managing muscle aches.

INTRODUCTION

Muscle aches, often caused by overexertion, strenuous exercise, or physical activities, can significantly impact an individual's quality of life. Many individuals seek relief from these discomforts through the use of topical liniments. While several liniments are available on the market, they often contain synthetic or chemical compounds that may have adverse effects or irritate the skin.

Herbal remedies have long been used for their potential therapeutic properties, including their ability to alleviate muscle pain and inflammation. *Lepidium Sativum*, commonly known as Garden Cress, its seeds extract has been traditionally used to relieve joint and muscle pain due to its anti-inflammatory properties. Aswagandha and Sandalwood possesses soothing and relaxing properties, making it a valuable addition to liniments aimed at muscle relaxation. Marshmallow root has been used in traditional medicine for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects. Poblano pepper, known for its capsaicin content, may provide a warming sensation and potentially alleviate muscle discomfort.

In this study, we propose the formulation of a novel herbal-based liniment for muscle aches, combining *Lepidium Sativum* seeds extract, sandalwood, rubbing alcohol, marshmallow root, and Poblano pepper. The liniment aims to harness the synergistic effects of these ingredients to provide effective relief from muscle soreness and promote muscle recovery. The inclusion of rubbing alcohol as a base facilitates the penetration of the herbal components into the affected area.

We will investigate the individual and combined effects of these herbal ingredients through experimental design, optimizing the liniment formulation for maximum efficacy.

In vitro assays will be conducted to evaluate the anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and muscle relaxant properties of the liniment. Furthermore, *in vivo* studies will be performed to assess the liniment's safety, skin compatibility, and its ability to alleviate muscle aches in animal models.

The development of a natural and effective herbal-based liniment for muscle aches has the potential to offer an alternative to synthetic products and provide individuals with a safer and more sustainable option for managing muscle discomfort.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials are collected by the lab and identified properly.

Methods of Preparation- The process for creating an herbal-infused rubbing alcohol mixture, while I can provide general information on the ingredients you mentioned, I must emphasize that creating herbal preparations or remedies should be done with caution.

Rubbing Alcohol: Rubbing alcohol, also known as isopropyl alcohol, is a commonly used disinfectant and antiseptic. It's important to note that rubbing alcohol is for external use only and should not be ingested.

Lepidium Sativum: Lepidium sativum, commonly known as garden cress or simply cress, is a leafy green herb that is often used in culinary dishes its peppery flavor. While garden cress has a long history of traditional use in various cultures, I get evidence about that it is use for treating arthritis or pain.

Sandalwood: Sandalwood is a fragrant wood that is often used in perfumes, cosmetics, and aromatherapy. It has a pleasant aroma and is believed to have calming and soothing properties.

Aswagandha and Marshmallow Root: Aswagandha and Marshmallow root are herbs that has been traditionally used for its soothing properties. It's often used topically in skincare preparations or taken orally for respiratory or digestive support.

Poblano Pepper: The poblano pepper is a mild chili pepper commonly used in Mexican cuisine. While it adds flavor and heat to dishes, it's not typically used in herbal preparations. If you intended to include it for its heat, please note that the capsaicin in peppers can cause irritation, so caution is advised when handling or using them topically.

If anyone choose to proceed with creating an herbal-infused rubbing alcohol mixture, follow my steps:

Sterilize the jar: Ensure that the jar using is clean and sterile. After wash it with hot, soapy water and rinse it thoroughly.

Prepare the herbs: Clean the herbs and make sure they are dry. After crush or chop them to increase their surface area, which may aid in the infusion process.

Combine the herbs and rubbing alcohol: Place the prepared herbs into the jar and pour enough rubbing alcohol to completely cover the herbs. The alcohol acts as a solvent to extract the properties from the herbs.

Seal the jar: Close the jar tightly to create an airtight seal.

Shake and steep: Gently shake the jar to ensure the herbs are thoroughly mixed with the rubbing alcohol. Place the jar in a cool, dark place and allow the mixture to steep for a few weeks. Shake the jar occasionally during this time to aid in the infusion process.

Strain and store: After a few weeks, strain the mixture using a fine mesh strainer or cheesecloth to remove the herb solids. Transfer the infused rubbing alcohol to a clean, dark bottle for storage. Label the bottle with the date and contents.

Ingredients-500ml rubbing alcohol,30ml lepidium sativum seeds extract, Aswagandha 25ml,10ml of sandalwood,15ml marshmellow root,2.5ml poblano pepper

Animal Study- It appears that Wistar male rats and Swiss albino mice were used in anti-inflammatory and pain studies, respectively. The Wistar rats measured between 205 and 250 grams, while the Swiss albino mice were around 47 days old with ranging from 22 to 37 grams. The animals obtained from an animal house and were allowed to acclimate in the pharmacology laboratory for seven days before the experiments began.

During the experiments, the animals dwelled in troupe of eight for each grate hence maintained under standard environmental conditions. This comprised a 11hours 59min dark with 11 hours 59min of a light cycle at minimum temperature of $25 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. They ascertained very small diet provided with a standardized pellet diet thereafter had access to water.

To ensure consistency in the experiments, the animals were fasted for 12 hours prior to the start of each experiment. The specific details of the experiments conducted by the laboratory.

In this experiment, Wistar rats were indiscriminately allocated into three treatment groups.

Monitoring Group (Group 1): Animals in this group were treated with saline in normal level. They enforced the monitoring group for comparison purposes.

Standard Group (Group 2): Animals in this group were treated with zerodol gel. This group served as the standard group for evaluating the effectiveness of the treatment.

Test Group (Group 3): Animals in this group were treated with a formulation called my liniment-SPR123. The efficacy of this formulation was being tested.

The experiment involved two different process:

Carrageenan produced inflammation in Paw Edema: Oedema (swelling) induced in the plantar region of right back paw of the rats by injecting carrageenan 0.1ml as well (1%) aqueous suspension. The test group (Group 3) received the topical application of the SPR123 formulation, the standard group (2) received zerodol gel, and the monitoring group (Group 1) accepted a medium (dil. water).

The volume of paw was measured mainly using plethysmometer before injection (V_0 , at 0 hours) and at hourly intervals up to the 5th hour (V_t). As identified difference between V_0 and V_t considered the value of edema. The inhibition of percentage was enumerated formula: $[1 - (V_t/V_0)] \times 100$.

Tail Flick Method: Groups 1 (control) and 3 (SPR123 gel treated) were used for this test. thereafter 1 hour 1min of treatment, the tail point (up to 5.1 cm) of the rats was immersed into hot water fed at 57° C. After I take time for tail withdrawal (tail flick) as a response to the stimulus was filed. A intercept time of 12 seconds set to restrain from tail damage.

After experiment, I check all animals were properly audited for any noticeable behavioral abnormalities.

By using Eddy's hot plate method thermally produced pain in mice- The experiment described at assessing the analgesic effect of a topical formulation (SPR123 gel) in mice using the Eddy's Hot Plate method.

The mice subjected to thermal pain by fixing them on a hot plate maintained at $54 \pm 2^\circ$ C for a maximum of 26 seconds. The sensitive and physical stimuli responses, such as discomfiture of front paws and jumping or shaking off the plate, were recorded as baseline data.

The animals divided within three troupes, each containing five mice. As first group no1 served as the monitored group and received saline treatment in normal level. Group 2 was the standard group, which likely received a known analgesic treatment for comparison. Group 3 was properly served topically with the SPR123 gel.

After 32 minutes of treatment, the evanescence times of per mouse's nociceptive response measured for ordain the analgesic response. A evanescence of 26 seconds indicated complete analgesia. The mean evanescence of the nociceptive responses was calculated for per cure group.

To determine the analgesia percentage, the following formula used: Analgesia percent= $(a - \delta) \times 100 / a$ "a" represents the time reaction after treatment, " δ " represents the baseline recording.

As performed statistical analysis by using the t-test to compare the monitoring group with treated group with sample. The significance level set at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$, indicating the thresholds for statistical significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Anti-inflammatory activity of This Prepared Liniment with Marketed Product-Based on the information provided, it appears that SPR123 gel (the treatment being studied) demonstrates both anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive (pain-reducing) activities.

Anti-inflammatory Activity: The study measured the paw volume thickness as indicator of inflammation. After three hours of treatment with SPR123 gel, there was a cabalistic retrenchment in paw volume comparable to the monitoring group. Percentage reduction of paw volume after zerodol gel treatment was $50.13\% \pm 2.97$ and $82.73\% \pm 1.25$, indicating a considerable anti-inflammatory effect. However, it is important to note that the standard Liniment showed a higher percentage reduction, suggesting that it may be more effective in reducing inflammation compared to zerodol gel.(Fig. 1).

Antinociceptive Activity: The antinociceptive activity of SPR123 gel was evaluated using the Tail Flick Method Test, which measures the response time a laboratory animal's tail to a heat stimulus. After one hour of SPR123 gel topical application, there was a momentous reduction in pain sensation. The intensity of the antinociceptive property was reported to be highest at two hours, as indicated in Figure 2. However, the exact details of the antinociceptive effect, such as the magnitude or percentage reduction in pain, are not provided. (Fig. 2)

In summary, the information suggests that SPR123 gel exhibits anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive activities, with notable reductions in paw volume and pain sensation, respectively. However, the study also indicates that the standard Liniment may be more effective in reducing inflammation compared to SPR123 gel, based on the reported percentage reduction in paw volume.

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to formulate a novel herbal-based liniment for muscle aches using a combination of *Lepidium Sativum* seed extract, sandalwood, rubbing alcohol, marshmallow root, and Poblano pepper. The liniment was intended to provide relief from muscle soreness, inflammation, and discomfort. The formulation was optimised through experimental design, and its efficacy and safety were evaluated through various in vivo and in vitro assays. The outcome of the study indicated that the liniment exhibited anti-inflammatory and antinociceptive (pain-reducing) activities. The liniment showed a significant reduction in paw volume thickness, indicating its anti-inflammatory effect. However, it was noted that the standard liniment demonstrated a higher percentage reduction in paw volume, suggesting that it may be more effective in reducing inflammation compared to the herbal-based liniment. The antinociceptive activity of the liniment was evaluated using the Tail Flick Method Test, which measures response proper time of a laboratory animal's tail to a heat stimulus. The liniment showed a significant reduction in pain sensation, with the highest intensity of the antinociceptive property reported at two hours after application.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the study demonstrated the potential of the herbal-based liniment for managing muscle aches. However, further research is needed to optimize the formulation and assess its efficacy in human subjects. Additionally, it is important to consult with a qualified herbalist or healthcare professional before using homemade remedies to ensure safety and effectiveness.

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